

Corrosion Studies: Small Arms and Cartridges

S. P. SALUJA

Ammunition Factory, Kirkee

Manuscript received December 1973; accepted 7 December 1974

Small arm is now regarded as a piece of machinery (modern fighting machine) and like other machinery, it is subject to wear and corrosion if not timely attended to. In fact this fascinating and indispensable fighting machine (gun/rifle) is actually a heat engine and as such it must generate considerable heat to produce necessary energy from combustion of a fixed propellant charge. Intense and sustained heat and action of hot gases reacting on gun barrel/bore can cause corrosion and this has to be accepted in the interest of efficiency. About one third of this energy is usefully utilized by the bullet alone during its flight up the bore.

As long as powder gases remain the means of propelling the projectile, certain design of material and certain laws of bullets' flight remain unchanged in small-arm, the problem of corrosion will always be there.

This paper deals all these aspects from the corrosion point of view.

CORROSION is a complex form of material deterioration. This deterioration is chiefly due to chemical reaction on metal surface with its environments. It takes best of human effort, energy and time to design, develop, manufacture and inspect standard ammunition and yet a little moisture can cause deterioration and make the ammunition (cartridge) dead in a very short time. It needs protection till its ultimate use, may be a 20 years period or so, depending on the exigency of the situation. Ammunition is expected to lie out under extreme and adverse conditions of temperature and humidity. Corrosion in fire-arms is a sign of neglect.

On firing a cartridge a pressure of 50,000 lbs. per sq. in. (p.s.i.) accompanied by a rise of high internal temperature develops within the chamber of a gun/rifle, to discharge its bullet out of bore of the gun. Although these conditions are operating for a few milliseconds only in the small-arms, yet these physico-chemical processes dictate the employment of right materials for cartridge as well as for small-arms particularly its barrel/bore from the corrosion point of view.

The cartridge and gun suffer no high temperature corrosion, harm, deformation or rusting due to such conditions of pressure and temperature prevailing, because their time of application is only a thousandth of a second; besides this there is transfer of heat energy to the walls of the barrel (by conduction, air and water cooling systems), the bullet utilizes about 30% (1/3) of the total energy during its flight upon the bore and rest of 70% is lost in other unavoidable ways.

The bore (soul) of gun is transversed by three substances—the bullet, the propellant (including its hot gases), and products released by the primer. Although the projection of the bullet and release of hot gases

is completed after a few milliseconds (0.002 second) around 3900°F temperature and 50,000 lbs (p.s.i.) pressure the operation die down instantly, yet all the above mentioned substances leave residues after their passage up the bore.

Corrosion in small-arm is due to the chemical reaction of hot gases emerging from combustion of primer and fixed powder charge in cartridge case and metallic fouling by the fouling of the bullet material of cartridge, while it travels up the bore of gun.

Modern nitro-cellulose high pressure smokeless powder on combustion produce only gaseous end-products such as carbon-dioxide, carbon-monoxide, hydrogen, nitrogen and ammonia besides some gummy matter and water-vapour. The latter evaporates under prevailing high temperature conditions and other end-products do not foul the bore nor cause its corrosion¹. Removal of gummy matter is done easily with the help of approved solvents/dopes given in Appendix (1).

Primers based on chlorate (potassium chlorate) produce on ignition potassium chloride, KCl, that is definitely corrosive. These much-used primers are sensitive and possess long duration of flash and sufficient gas volume. This salt is akin to common-salt (table-salt), NaCl, and causes corrosion on barrel/bore steel after picking up moisture from the surroundings, just like a moist common salt on the tip of the table-knife rusts and corrodes it. The deposit of this salt always finds its way into the rough cracks and fissures of the bore surface where it dangerously lurks as invisible substance to cause corrosion². Extensive studies undertaken by Huff has proved that at temperature 30° and humidity from 68% to 76% cause definite corrosion³.

Remedy for this lies in dissolving out the deposited salt with the help of water for which it has a great

affinity. It dissolves readily in water, preferably warm in which it is easily washed out. Additional advantage of using warm water is quick drying of the barrel surface due to heat of evaporation. Subsequently the bore is made dry by rubbing up and down fannel patches and then slightly oiled with a patch. Finally the bore surface is wiped, cleaned of oil with a dry patch to avoid any eventual rusting.

The tendency of a bore/barrel to collect metallic fouling depends on three main factors: (a) smoothness or roughness of the bore, (b) the temperature prevailing and (c) the material of bullet envelop (jacket). A badly pitted and rough barrel would obviously collect more metallic fouling than one which is in good condition. Cupro-nickel (80/20—Cu/Ni) envelope foul more as nickel possesses a far greater affinity for steel of the barrel than lead or other material, when used for envelopes. The adoption of gilding metal as bullet envelop materials has satisfactorily solved corrosion problem. In fact, everything being equal, gilding metal (80/20—Cu/Zn) gives an extremely thin wash of copper colour plating to the bore surface, under prevailing conditions and this thin plating (hardly visible) protects the bore surface from further rusting of steel⁴. Lead bullets (unjacketed) also foul the bore surface, as lead is comparatively soft. It is rightly said, "The lead bullets never 'lead' up a barrel; as nickel jacketed bullets would 'nickel' one up"⁵.

Metallic fouling is removed by careful application for 5-7 mins. freshly prepared ammonia dope (Appendix 1) on the affected surface and rubbing the surface clean with dry patches, next applying an oiled-soaked patch on the surface and finally wipe clean it with a dry patch.

The cartridge: Corrosion pattern obturation device that minimizes corrosion:

Obturation is the function of brass centre fire cartridges. It helps to minimise/arrest the occurrence of corrosion in small-arms in a unique way. Special heat- and surface treatments meted out to the cartridge (in which all the components—primer, powder charge and bullet are enclosed in the case) bestow correct obturation of its components at the required time and place. Primer (cap composition loaded under pressure into pellet) top is well protected against moisture by putting a varnished disc (paper/tinfoil) and sealing it with a drop of varnish and drying it. Primer assembly in case of cap-chamber is again sealed with a drop of varnish suitably, to ensure its water-proofness. Likewise before bulleting, the neck of the case is varnished with water-proof asphaltite petroleum coat that ensures a good and effective seal against moisture. This simple looking case presents a clean dry surface without dint, dirt/dust or tool-marks, where corrosion can have no foot-hold even in humid surroundings.

The design features including heat-treatment undergone by the various components of cartridge help to reduce the residual stresses that could be inflicted on them during their manufacture, to

safeguard against stress corrosion cracking, as revealed by mercurous nitrate test.

(1) *Cartridge case*: The brass cartridge thus possesses adequate strength and elasticity to obturate satisfactorily under hot gas working conditions. This centre-fire brass cartridge case is designed to suitably accommodate (without causing stress corrosion) in one water-proof unit—a sealed primer in its relatively hard cap-chamber, progressively burning smokeless powder charge safe in its body and hard-drawn solid bullet in its soft neck till its flight.

When a cartridge is fired, the gas expands the case and exerts pressure on all directions, but this expansion is always within the elastic limit of brass. In such an unique way, the case, primer and bullet function to protect the small-arms from the warmth of hot and corrosion gases.

(a) *Case*: Under the prevailing gas pressure the case gets correct obturation; its body hugs the gun-chamber² and its soft neck enables timely release of tight-fit bullet. When gas pressure falls, in splits of a second, it is unseated (easy ejection of spent case) without causing undue stresses (stress corrosion).

(b) *Primer*: Under ignition heat, the walls of primer expand against the walls of case-cap-chamber, preventing any gas leak or escape to the rear thereby protects the rear delicate and automatic mechanism of the gun/rifle from pitting corrosion around the striker head.

(c) *Bullet*: The solid gilding metal jacketed bullet resists altogether melting or high temperature corrosion and withstands high chamber pressure (about 18 tons per sq. in.) acting on its base, gives it a quick push to 'set up' and barricade the new gushing gases thereby safeguarding the bore and giving a longer barrel life.

Imagine the plight of gun, had the force (50,000 p.s.i. pressure) be permitted for a whole second! The resulting speedy flying back of the gun would mow down everyone of its path. The extent and types of corrosion cannot be foretold! In case a lower pressure is developed, under gas working conditions, the powder charge may not even completely burn and bullet may not even leave timely and struck up towards the muzzle. The corrosion pattern then can be well imagined.

Conclusion

Ordnance engineers explosive chemists, corrosion and ammunition experts are ever busy in evolving various combination of newer compositions. Priming composition that should instantly give excellent ignition, maximum gas volume and large plus very hot flame. High temperature corrosion can be substantially reduced by using cool propellants. But difficulty arises because a cool burning powder bulks larger than a hotter one and occupies more space in the case.

SALUJA : CORROSION STUDIES : SMALL ARMS AND CARTRIDGES

Developments are aimed at to evolve newer smokeless progressive burning powders that would give higher pressure without smoke and flash or smoke and flash reduced to minimum tending to zero. Work continues towards developing 'non-corrosive non-mercuric primer' that should give large flash and high gas volume.

These newer powerful primers when used in conjunction with smokeless propellant powders would not foul or cause rusting of the bore but would prove entirely reliable and remarkably successful in every way and thus constitute the greatest improvement in the small-arm ammunition.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Padmashri Shri O. P. Bhal, General Manager, Ammunition Factory, Kirkee, for his kind permission and guidance in presenting this paper.

References

1. E. B. CHARLES, "Principles of Fire-arms", 1947, p. 103.
2. MAJ. J. S. HATCHER, "Hatchers' Note Book", 1957, p. 347.
3. W. J. HUFF, "Technical Paper on Causes and Prevention of After Corrosion", Govt. Printing Office, Publication 1922 (Ref. cited by Maj J. S. Hatcher, "Hatchers' Note Book, 1957, p. 346.
4. COL. WHELEN TOWNSEND, "Small Arms—Design and Ballistics", 1945, Vol. II, p. 224.
5. MAJ. SIR GERNALD BURRARD, "Identification of Fire Arms and Forensic Ballistics", 1956, p. 163.

Appendix I

Metallic fouling-barrel cleaner-solvent

The process of corrosion in a fire-arm is slow and gradual, requiring several hours/days in presence of fouling materials when exposed to over 50% humid condition and atmosphere bearing oxygen derived from air. In a fire-arm such a corrosion is always a sign of neglect in cleaning due to ignorance or carelessness in employing the approved cleaners. After using standard cleaners, protection against corrosion is secured by making the surface smooth and clean and subsequently making it dry and then oiling.

1) This solvent should be applied fresh always on the deposit surface for effective working.

Ammonium persulphate	— 1 ounce
Ammonium carbonate	—200 grains
Strong ammonia (28%)	— 6 ounces
Water	— 4 ounces

Applying carefully fresh solution for 10 min. on the affected portion. Quickly wash with water, wipe clean and oil. Wipe clean again with 2 or 3 dry patches.

2) Nitro-solvent : That dissolves gummy residue from N.C. powders :

Acetone	—1 part	To every 800 ml, add 250 g of anhydrous lanolin, stir it with turpentine oil and add acetone.
Kerosene (Pratt's Astral oil)	—1 part	
Sperm oil	—1 part	
Turpentine (mineral sprit)	—1 part	

3) Three special abressive pastes made for the purpose of removing metallic fouling from the bore are : (a) "Motti Paste, B.S.A.", (b) "Cunirid" and (c) "Coswell". "Motti" is highly active and hence is not safe to use often.

4) Grease cause uneven velocities and extremely high chamber pressure. Application of grease or vaseline on bullet is not advisable as it is positively dangerous. Pressure increases from safety limit of 50,000 pounds/sq.in. to 75,000 pounds/sq.in. (dangerous level.).

5) *Polarised oil* : The latest cleaners are based on polarised oils. When such a cleaner is placed on a wet metal surface, it breaks the film of the water and sinks right down through it to the metal surface and clings to it. Such oils have a strong affinity for metal and at the same time would combine readily with water.

These polarised oil compounds have enough water in their make-up to dissolve the primer salt and at the same time they are sufficiently oily to retard rusting. A very popular one is an emulsion of water and Turkey red oil.

Best gun-oil : An equivalent to Japanese gun oil is :

Oleic Acid	— 16%
Neutral saponified oil	— 24%
Nitro-benzene	— 6%
Refined kerosine oil	} — 54%
Amyl acetate	